

This concept note evolved during the COVID-19 pandemic when we realized the need to integrate our work on the Indian Knowledge System with our scientific endeavor to develop the Thoreau Lab youth program at Walden Pond. The concept note was presented 1) at the Thoreau lab meeting at Walden Pond campus, in November 2022, and 2) to Professor Kapil Kapoor in New Delhi, in March 2021, and submitted to the Government of India, Central Ministry of Education and External Affairs, June 2023.

Expanding the Indian Knowledge System inspired biomedical science in the USA

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Summary: To meet the complex challenge of the 21st century, science needs the support of philosophy. Yet, modern scientists, especially biomedical scientists, rarely seek philosophical guidance to gain conceptual insight or formulate new ideas/theories on basic science as well as public health. In this context, Indian Knowledge System (IKS) may play a key role as it is enriched in great philosophical thoughts. We and others have applied philosophical ontology to gain insight into stem cell biology, especially stemness (the identity and state of a stem cell) [1-4] (Figure 1-2). Importantly, by implementing the Vedic philosophy of “Avatarvada” and “Sataavata Tarka” (Figure 3), we have gained insight into stem cell altruism and stem cell niche defense [3-5] as well as global health diseases like tuberculosis and covid19 [3], [5-6]. Moreover, based on Vedic Altruism’s metaphysic of community healing through temple networks (Figure 4), we have developed a hybrid digital therapeutic regime for bio-social medicine, an emerging area of global health practice [7-8]. These are a few examples of the practical applicability of Vedic philosophy inspired biological altruism in clarifying and formulating new concepts in stem cell biology and its application in diseases such as tuberculosis and cancer. Significantly, these examples shine the need for the IKS for modern science to progress. In this context, as per new UGC guidelines, we have developed a Vedic Altruism based Project course for the undergraduate and graduate students of IKS. We have achieved this success through the KaviKrishna lab at Guwahati (est. 2010), and its sister lab, the Thoreau Lab for Global

Health at Lowell, Massachusetts (est. 2018), plus two philosophical centers, the Suad Muni Pond campus of rural Sualkuchi (near Guwahati), and Walden Pond campus of Concord (near Boston, Massachusetts). The Walden Pond is the site, where the famous American Vedic philosopher Henry David Thoreau meditated on Hindu philosophy. Reviving the traditional Vedic Philosophy and Science study at Walden Pond has been a key mission for us since 2015 when Dr. Bikul Das talked about this plan in a speech at Harvard University (<https://youtu.be/XyUhs6rCJcM>). Thoreau and his mentor Emerson did regular ancient Indian philosophical and scientific discussions at Harvard, but that tradition is somewhat lost or not being fully utilized for the advancement of modern biomedical science, especially stem cell science. We now would like to revive Thoreau's tradition by expanding Thoreau Lab for Global Health to Kendall Square, a world-renowned hub of innovation, ingenuity and imagination (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kendall_Square) that serve as the tech hub of MIT/Harvard and allied institutions, including Forsyth Institute, where Dr. Das worked as a faculty for five years. The Thoreau Lab at Kendall Square will then connect to greater India's emerging IKS academics through KaviKrishna Laboratory, Guwahati. Through these two centers as one hub, the International Vedic Center of Health Sciences (Figure 5), we would like to accomplish the following objectives in the next three years.

- 1. Consolidate our gain in the application of IKS in bio-medical science (Figure 1-3).**
- 2. Consolidate our gain in the application of IKS in Public Health and Global Health Theory (Figure 4).**
- 3. Development of an IKS based Medical Humanities research project for USA students interested to pursue short term research in rural India.**

1.0 Background and Preliminary work:

Ancient Indian Knowledge System (IKS) was a thriving source of inspiration during the age of the Renaissance and continues to inspire diverse branches of modern sciences. However, the great potential of exploring IKS to design modern scientific experiments and theories, especially in the stem cell field has not been fully realized. Our long-term goal has been to create a bridge between the top scientific hubs of USA, and the rural philosophical heart of India (where the ancient IKS still thrives as a living tradition for knowledge development) to promote the use of IKS in modern scientific experimental designs and innovation. For the last 12 years, we have formed the bridge by forming collaborative projects with Stanford University, California and Forsyth Institute (a Harvard University

affiliated institution located in Kendall Square, Cambridge, MA) to use a piece of IKS, the Vedic Altruism to design innovative experiments in stem cell sciences. The Vedic Altruism (Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra) evolved in Kamarupa, a center of Vedic culture since the time of Ramayana. It is an oral tradition of Tantra believed to be rooted in the Madhu Vidya of Rig Veda [7-8], and hence known as Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra or Vedic Altruism [8], [13]. Our efforts and success to transform the philosophy of Vedic Altruism to a scientific hypothesis were nicely acknowledged in the background information of an international press release made by Elsevier in 2021 [9], as well as mentioned in a scientific paper published in Am J Pathology, 2021 [3]. Vedic altruism was also mentioned in a doctoral thesis of Harvard University, 2022 [4] as an inspiration for the research work on stem cell altruism. The public also found great interest in our work on transforming a piece of Hindu philosophy to stem cell science e.g. a news item published in the Times Crest weekly issue of the Times of India [10]. Below, a brief description of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra and its application in bio-medical science as well as public health science is given.

1.1.1 Transformation of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra metaphysic to testable scientific hypothesis on stem cell altruism (Figure 1-2):

Vedic Jiva Upakara tantra (Vedic Altruism) is a nearly extinct philosophical tradition of ancient Kamarup's Vedic Philosophical discourse. This discourse produced great philosophical work such as Amritasiddha, Hevajra tantra, Akul Vira Tantra, Kalika Purana and Yogini Tantra. At the core of Vedic Altruism is the concept of "Avatar kosha", a transient kosha of the mind-body complex, as per the Vedic Panchakosha system (Annamaya, Pranamaya, Manomaya, Vijnanamaya and Anandamaya) [5], [8]. "Avatar-kosha" facilitates the flow of Ojash, the subtle energy fluid of healing. Lord Krishna mentioned Ojasa in Bhagavad Gita: In all living being in this earth, I permeate as Ojasa (gam avishya cha bhutani dharayamy aham ojasa; Gita 15.13). Avatar Kosha concept of JUT has borrowed the idea from Vedantic Philosophy that states that during stress, the living organism acquires a higher state, known as Avatar to defend their clan (gana) from stress. Inspired by this concept of "Avatar Kosha" of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT), Vedic Philosopher and poet Krishna Ram Das of Kamrupa, wrote many poetry such as "Sonali Nakhar Jui (Fire of Golden Nail)" as well as "Manavatar Tantra (The Tantra of Humanity)" [5], [8], [10-14]. The philosopher and his friends, including Acharya Dayal Krishna Bora, Jagat Ghora and Hem Bhai hypothesized that like ordinary humans undergo immense transformation of an Avatar to protect the earth from atrocities (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Avatar>),

a few cells (Nigudah as per JUT) in the animal body may also transform into Avatar or altruistic cells to protect the body from infectious pathogens as well as cancer cells [5], [8], [10-14]. Dr. Das briefly mentioned the “Avatar Kosha” in a book about anti-oxidants published in the year 2000 [15], and utilized the metaphysics of JUT to develop a concept of knowledge emergence in 2003 [16]. He then utilized JUT philosophy based “satavata tarka” (Figure 3) [supplementary note of reference 5] to design experiments on biological stress, which led him to identify the altruistic behavior of human embryonic stem cells in 2012 at Stanford University [2],[10],[17]. Like an “Avatar”, the altruistic stem cells are robust, and cytoprotective to the stem cell pool in the niche [2-3], [8-10]. Subsequently, Dr. Das and his team applied the philosophy of Vedic Altruism to describe stemness, the property that defines stem cells [5], [18-19]. Accordingly, depending on the level of stress in the tissue, stemness could be altruistic (an intrinsic attribute of stem cell mediated cytoprotection independent of its environment), intrinsic (Swakosha; intrinsic attribute independent of external environment), and extrinsic (parakosha; intrinsic attribute controlled by external environment) [5],[18-19]. Such an approach has helped us to identify stem cell niche defense mechanisms having relevance in TB and cancer, as well as “Nigudah-immunity [2-6], [19], and cancer immunotherapy [20]. The relevance of JUT based “Satavata tarka” (Figure 3) in transforming Vedic philosophy to scientific discourse has been thoroughly described in the supplementary note of a pre-print publication in 2020 [5]. Based on this idea of stem cell altruism, four graduate students completed their Ph.D. thesis and four students are currently pursuing their Ph.D. degree under the guidance of Dr. Bikul Das from KaviKrishna Lab. These students are registered in various collaborative Institute of India, as well as USA. Our endeavour and efforts have been acknowledged by the American Journal of Pathology through a press release to report the identification of altruistic stem cell defense mechanism of lung alveolar stem cell niche [3], [9].

1.1.2 Application of Vedic philosophical metaphysics in public health science (Figure 3):

Madhu Vidya of Rig Veda and Upanishad is probably the first philosophy of public health science: the community is honey for me, and I am honey for the community. Based on Vedic philosophy inspired public health science, many Hindu and Buddhist temple complexes have been serving as public health centers, especially for rural South Asia and South East Asia. Dr. Bikul Das and clinical team have been researching this temple complex-based public health care through the KaviKrishna telemedicine care (KTC) located at the Suad Muni campus of KaviKrishna Lab. The two decades of research employing case studies, grounded theory, and ethno-phenomenography have

uncovered a Vedic Altruism-based public health approach. At the heart of this approach is the use of a Hindu temple network of rural Kamarupa, the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN) [7-8], [21]. The practitioners of Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT) utilized the IKIN to activate Avatar kosha in the community [5], [7-8]. We have set up a community-based participatory research (CBPR) in our clinic back in 1994 initially to do the cancer disparity research, which then unfolded into the study of the IKS-based Jiva Upakara Tantra, especially the community service or sewa-induced Avatar kosha. Two of our Ph.D. students are currently studying the metaphysics of this community-induced Avatar kosha as a novel model of bio-social medicine [7-8], [21], an emerging field of modern public health approach. The students developed a clinical score to measure Avatar kosha by utilizing four well-established clinical scores: SF-36, Rosenberg scale of self-esteem, SACS score of collaboration, and Hamilton scale of anxiety [7-8]. Using the patient network of Dr. Bikul Das' telemedicine clinic, the Ph.D. students have developed an "IKIN digital therapeutic regime" that provides weekly virtual clinic, lifestyle coaching on nutrition/herbal gardening, digital monitoring of health (i.e. blood pressure, weight, hemoglobin, and blood sugar), focused group discussion, online weekly Nigudah yoga, and online rehabilitation program [7-8] for the people connected to the IKIN. Dr. Das' telemedicine care team managed n=1500 Covid19 (stage I and II) subjects by using this IKIN digital therapeutic device [7], [21-24]. We are now using this IKIN digital therapeutic regime in the clinical part of a study on the evolution of Multi-drug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) funded by Department of Biotechnology, govt. of India [7] [21]. Thus, we are applying the IKS-based public health approach to develop the next generation of digital therapeutic regime, which can be further developed as an AI enabled point-of-care device/application.

2.0 OBJECTIVES:

1. Consolidate our gain on the application of Vedic Philosophy in basic and clinical biomedical science (Figure 1-3).

Our goal has been the meaningful use of IKS based philosophy to gain novel insight into scientific enquires such as the biology of stem cells. To this end, as stated above, we have succeeded in gaining insight on the altruistic behavior of stem cells by applying the metaphysics of Vedic Altruism. Our work has been published in numerous publications in high-impact scientific journals (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=KaviKrishna%20Laboratory%2C%20India>). We will continue to expand our work on stem cell altruism-based research in stem cell regenerative medicine [2, 3, 25-26], cancer [19, 27-30], and infectious diseases [3-6, 31]. However robust and thorough

investigation is required to build and bring forward this new field of stem cell altruism towards translational research. This can be achieved through in vitro, in vivo experiments, and clinical research in KKL, including a cGMP facility for the application of stem cells in therapeutics. We also have developed a rural cancer patient network system through KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care (KTC), Sualkuchi, Assam through the last two decades of dedicated work. Our intended extensive research requires better infrastructure, research facilities, and resources in KKL and KTC. Hence through this proposal, we wish to enhance and refurbish our laboratory resources at KKL. Furthermore, through the Thoreau Lab at Kendall Square, we aim to expand our collaboration with Ragon Institute at Harvard/MIT for a MDR-TB research project, which stemmed from our pioneering work on the stem cell basis of TB dormancy and reactivation [6]. Ragon Institute was very supportive to Dr. Das' work on stem cell altruism based TB research by providing him with space at the BSL-3 core lab between 2014-2017, where Ph.D. students of his previous lab at Forsyth Institute worked. Thoreau Lab would be able to re-ignite these collaborations to take forward our work on stem cell altruism.

2. Consolidate our gain on the application of Vedic Philosophy in Public Health Science and Global Health Theory (Figure 4).

We plan to take the Vedic Altruism based public health approach to the academic research community at Harvard/MIT, and allied Institutions. For example, our strategy of re-igniting collaboration with Ragon Institute and Forsyth Institute will not only enhance our ongoing work on stem cell altruism, but also introduce the IKIN digital therapeutic regime [7] to physicians and scientists of Kendall Square hub of biomedical research. At KaviKrishna lab, we plan to conceptualize the IKIN digital therapeutic regime as an AI-enabled point-of-care device/application, and then develop a collaborative plan with both Indian and USA-based labs to transform this concept into translational research for product development. Importantly, our goal is to apply this IKIN digital therapeutic regime in rural Massachusetts' yoga center networks to study the potential effectiveness of Avatar kosha based community public health measures. We aim to start this project among the elderly of Concord town, where the Walden Pond Campus of Thoreau Lab is located. We would also like to expand our ongoing collaboration with Boston University to serve the minority population, including the Indigenous American population, through the IKIN digital therapeutic regime.

The accumulating data of our IKIN-based work in rural Kamarupa, and also rural Massachusetts may help us to develop a comprehensive theory of Global health as discussed in the future direction section of a research paper presented in the Northeast Research Conclave held at IIT Guwahati in May

2022 [7]. Noted that at present, Humanity does not have a comprehensive theory on Global health, and therefore, it is challenging to study the impact of pollution/climate change on Global health. We will work with the public health experts of India and the US to introduce our approach to developing a comprehensive theory on Global Health as outlined in detail in Dr. Das' three books [8], [13-15], a research article on indigenous culture and globalization [16], and field research work on IKIN [7], [21-24].

3. Development of an IKS based Medical Humanities research project for USA students interested to pursue short term research in rural India.

The work of objectives 1 and 2 involves cutting-edge laboratory research as well as community health care, which is an ideal setup for the students of Medical Humanities to do fieldwork. The Medical Humanities is an emerging field in the USA. Baylor College of Medicine has developed a course on Medical Humanities centered on the role of Christian spirituality in health care. We are developing a Medical Humanities program centered on the role of Hindu Philosophy in health care, as well as bioethics. Our bioethics paper provides an IKS based ethical viewpoint on embryo editing [11]. Moreover, the IKS based Medical Humanities program will be benefitted from the Vedic Altruism methodology of suppositional reasoning (Satavata Tarka) as narrated in Figure 3. Two Ph.D. students and two research interns are involved in the fieldwork at the Walden Pond campus of Thoreau Lab, USA, and the Suad Muni Pond campus of KaviKrishna Lab, Sualkuchi, Assam, India to develop the overseas field research program of Medical Humanities course. One of the students has recently submitted a Ph.D. project, "A Medical Humanities Approach to Study the Indigenous Knowledge System Based Vedic Jiva Upakara Cikitsa Tantra of Kamrupa" to the Center of Indian Knowledge System at IIT Guwahati. Two US based high school students completed short term internship, while a post high school student of Massachusetts completed a 5 month long gap year period at the Suad Muni Pond campus of KaviKrishna Lab. We have recently co-sponsored an IKS seminar held at IIT Guwahati, where the USA student participated, and presented a short paper and oral talk on the IKSbased medical humanities program [32]. Importantly, one of our Ph.D. students at KaviKrishna Lab visited the Thoreau lab for two weeks and participated in the Vedic philosophical discussion at the Walden Pond campus of the Thoreau lab. The Ph.D. student is pursuing her Ph.D. in stem cell altruism at IIT Guwahati, and at the same time working with the Center of IKS at the IIT to develop a course on IKS based Medical Humanities. These are part of our strategic plan to further our ongoing collaboration with the IIT Guwahati to develop a Ph.D. program on IKS based Medical Humanities.

This Ph.D. program will be taken to the proposed “International Vedic Center for Health Sciences” at Ragon Institute of MIT/Harvard, thereby introducing a Hindu philosophy-oriented Medical Humanities Program in North America’s Medical Institutes. We believe that the prospective US students will benefit by interacting with the students doing Ph.D. work on stem cell altruism at KaviKrishna Lab.

3.0 OUR STRATEGIC PLAN FOR PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION:

We will accomplish the proposed task by expanding the Thoreau Lab for Global Health from its current location at the M2D2 incubator of the University of Massachusetts to Ragon Institute at Harvard/MIT, Cambridge, MA. This task can be accomplished by taking a rented lab space at Ragon Institute, where Dr. Das already had a BSL-3 lab space back in 2014-2017. For this purpose of renting and functioning at Ragon Institute, we are working on raising \$5 million. Additionally, US \$0.7 million is required to maintain the Walden Pond campus of Thoreau Lab; this pond was the site for the Vedic philosophy study of American philosophers Henry David Thoreau and Ralph Emerson. We have built strong community relations with the people of Concord and Lincoln, the area near Walden Pond (20 miles west of Harvard campus). Importantly, we need \$0.5 million to upgrade the India facility, the KaviKrishna Laboratory. The up gradation will help to make the lab, a world class stem cell lab, and also accommodate American students and researchers of Thoreau Lab and other labs of MIT/Harvard. These American students will be able to perform field studies in science, Vedic philosophy, and Medical Humanities in the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complexes. Thus, a total of Rs 60 crores are required to implement the strategic plan in India and USA.

4.0 EXPECTED RESULTS:

Research on stem cell altruism is a part of the ongoing research on biological altruism, a key field of evolutionary biology. Therefore, we expect that our efforts will stimulate a worldwide debate and research on Vedic philosophical views on biological altruism. The “International Vedic Center for Health Sciences” will be a meeting point of Vedic philosophers and modern scientists/students at Kendall Square of USA. Interestingly, the scientific community at Kendall Square is aware of the work on stem cell altruism at Dr. Das’ lab at Forsyth Institute (2014-2018). This pre-existing network of scientists will get a boost following the setting up of the Vedic philosophy center, and will be enthusiastic to visit and experience IKS through KaviKrishna Lab’s Suad Muni Pond campus located

in rural Sualkuchi, a historic silk village plus renowned for the meeting point of ancient Vedic tradition of Kamarupa.

We expect that our efforts will bring forward a new IKS-based scientific discourse on biological altruism in a global scientific platform. Since the introduction of the term altruism by Auguste Comte, evolutionary psychologists, evolutionary biologists, and ethologists have debated the basis of social and biological altruism. Although biological altruism has been explained in terms of group or kin selection, and anthropologists reported the phenomena of altruistic behavior among humans, and ant as narrated in Edward Wilson's groundbreaking book, *Sociobiology: The New Synthesis*, there is little consensus on altruism among modern evolutionary biologists. The dominant school of evolutionary biologist agrees that altruism contradicts the essence of Darwin's theory of Natural Selection. In this context, Vedic Altruism introduces another dimension to the phenomena of altruism i.e. the altruistic agent needs to reprogram to a higher state of power first and then sacrifice that power for group fitness [5], [8-14], [22]. Thus, the phenomenological and ontological insight of Vedic Altruism has the potential for an immense contribution to bringing novel insight into Darwin's theory of natural selection.

Moreover, studying the underlying metaphysics of Vedic Altruism or JUT may provide new insight into different problems that now confront the stem cell research community. We expect that the centers will greatly contribute to the research on stem cell niche defense, microbes, and cancer, a new and emerging field of stem cell research. We also expect that the KaviKrishna lab will become a top stem cell lab in the world through its exclusive focus on stem cell altruism. The team's innovative ideas and therapeutic findings including stem cell altruism based immunotherapy (BCG) against cancer (19), and vaccination against TB and Covid19 could be patented and commercialized through our initiative. The high cost of anti-cancer immunotherapy discourages patients to opt for this drug, thereby, impacting the demand and anticipated to hinder the immunotherapy's market growth. The global cellular immunotherapy market is expected to grow from \$3.68 billion in 2021 to \$4.30 billion in 2022 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17%. CAR-T therapy is a type of cellular immunotherapy and only two have been approved in the USA. The price of Yescarta and Kymriah is more than \$350,000 per treatment in the USA, which is highly unaffordable for a majority of patients, especially low income individuals and patients of developing countries like India. However, our assessment suggests that the CAR-T therapy cost can be reduced from \$350k to \$35k in India. Our ASC based cellular therapy could be affordable for Indian patients and will be very affordable for

many Americans. Therefore, we need a budget of 10 crore to set up the cGMP facility at KaviKrishna Lab, Guwahati to provide our ASC based immunotherapy to many needy cancer patients.

In terms of public health sciences, our ongoing work on Vedic Altruism based public health activities of Hindu temple complexes in rural Kamrup of Assam will generate great enthusiasm in the Kendall Square research community on developing a sustainable public health care model. Moreover, our work on the IKIN digital therapeutic regime as an AI enabled point-of-care device/application will be an innovative “Made in India” product that may transform the biosocial based health care in the USA. The market size of such digital devices/applications is estimated to be more than 70% of the projected global population with internet access by 2028.

Our work on IKS based Medical Humanities will provide a new purpose to the newly emerging field of Medical Humanities: take a biosocial look on medicine. KaviKrishna is trying to bring multiple fields together to provide students to experience medical practice. Furthermore, the main mandate of KaviKrishna is to convert philosophy into science. These values are at the core of KaviKrishna itself, just as they are at the core of a Knowledge System. Incorporating such IKS based values in the Medical Humanities course will take our philosophical insights into the core of medical school curriculum in USA.

Finally, the research work generated at the proposed International Vedic Center of Health Sciences will greatly contribute to the current momentum of Indo-US partnership and leverage Indian philosophy and knowledge system towards a new dimension in the domain of biomedical scientific exploration as well as clinical benefits.

We require philanthropic support to upgrade the KaviKrishna Lab in Guwahati and its rural campus of cancer care unit in Sualkuchi and Hajo. We aim to sustain this project through grants and philanthropic donations, as well as educational/training revenues. Our success will further enable the philosophers of the Vedic ages to take re-birth in scientific projects across USA and especially in the MIT/Harvard ecosystem.

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Figure 1: Transformation of the philosophy of Vedic altruism to the science of stem cell altruism, KaviKrishna's journey from 1992 to 2021

A. The idea on Avatar Kosha of Vedic Altruism, 1992

B. The evidence of "Avatar Kosha" mechanism in human embryonic stem cells derived Altruistic stem cells, 2012

C. Press release by Stanford University of California about the identification of Altruistic stem cells.

D. Oncology, as per the Vedanta

E. Press release by Elsevier and EurekaAlert! of American Association of Advancement of Science (AAAS) about the identification of lung mesenchymal stem cell derived Altruistic stem cells, 2021

The Background notes of the Press release recognizes the contribution of Vedic Jiva UpakarVada (Vedic Altruism) in the development of the concept of stem cell altruism.

NEWS RELEASE 16-JUN-2021

Stem cells may hold a key to developing new vaccines against COVID-19

Coronavirus activates a stem cell-mediated defense mechanism that reactivates dormant TB in a mouse model and has implications for developing new vaccines and avoiding a global TB pandemic, report investigators in The American Journal of Pathology

Peer-Reviewed Publication
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Background notes

This study of stem cell altruism was inspired by the Indian Vedantic Philosophical theory of altruistic behavior, which was referred to in the poem "Fire of Golden Nail" written by Vedic philosopher and poet Krishna Ram Das of Kamrupa, India, noted the study's authors. Poet Krishna Ram Das conceptualized the idea while undergoing surgery for throat cancer and initiated the KaviKrishna Foundation to test his idea through vigorous scientific research.

"Proving altruism in mammalian cell biology is a challenging task, as we faced years of resistance from colleagues," commented Bikul Das. "Altruism is about group selection, which is very challenging to demonstrate at the molecular level. However, the idea of altruism that we are describing here is the philosophical view of Vedic Jiva Upakarvada (Vedic altruism), a part of Vedantic thought that states that during stress, the living organism acquires a higher state, known as 'Avatar.' The mandate of the KaviKrishna laboratory is to take this philosophical view forward to modern biology, specifically to develop a philosophical and social theory on global health.

Figure 2: KaviKrishna lab has made key discoveries since 2012 in collaboration with Thoreau Lab for Global Health, University of Massachusetts Lowell, Forsyth Institute, Kendal Square, Cambridge, MA, and Stanford University

Years	Reference number (Pages 9-10)
2000	15
2003	25
2008 (a)	26
2008 (b)	27
2012	2
2013	6
2015	31
2016	18
2019	28
2021	3
2022	19

In this book, *The Science Behind Squalene*, published in the year 2000, and printed by the University of Toronto press, Dr. Das mentioned the idea of “Avatar Kosha”, “stem cell niche defense”, and “stem cell altruism”. Dr. Das did his PhD based on the stem cell related ideas described in the book. This book was his first strategy to bring the Vedic philosophy based scientific pursuit to the scientific community of North America.

Figure 3: The application of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic Altruism) based suppositional reasoning (Satvata tarka) in formulating scientific hypothesis, and experimental designs in our research at KaviKrishna lab.

A. The Guru Asana Vyuha component of Satvata Tarka. The dynamic interaction between two distinct ideas (Dharana) leads to Satvata sanjog or Nadi (realistic connection) that enables knowledge emergence (Prajna Agan). **B.** The seven steps of Satvata tarka.

C. Experimental plan to identify extracellular vesicles in aerosol of smear negative pulmonary TB subjects based on the Satvata Tarka method of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic Altruism).

D. News report in Assam Tribune about the design of scientific experiments based on Vedic altruism, November 18, 2020

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.11.14.382572v1>

Figure 4: Application of Vedic Altruism in public health science

A. The Sualkuchi-Hajo-Kamakhya cultural complex along the ancient Vedic Silk Road.

It seems that pre-Vedic and Vedic culture spread from North West India to North East India via Kashmir and Tibet along this silk route. Therefore, it can be termed as the “Vedic Silk Road.” Evidence for its existence includes the Kalita tribe of Kamrup and their Vedic culture, Muga silk culture of Sualkuchi, and the Vedic Tantra philosophy of Kamarupa, Tibet, Kashmir, and South East Asia.

Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex located north of Kamakhya temple, Guwahati.

The **Vedic Silk road** starts at Kushi of Central Asia and ends at Angkor Wat of Cambodia, the largest Vishnu temple in the world constructed in 6th century, contemporary to Hayagriva Vishnu temple of Kamrup/India. Detailed research is described in the book “Akion Bigvanir Hindutva Yatra” (Hindutva Journey of a Scientist, Dr. Bikul Das, 2018, page 510).

B. The concept of Avatar Kosha based community healing in the ancient temple complexes of Sualkuchi-Hajo-Kamakhya cultural complex

Vedic altruism is a mind-body-based bio-social medicine approach based on “Avatar Kosha”, which, according to Vedic Altruism, is a transient kosha of the Pancha kosha system.

Avatar Kosha is altruistic, as it enhances the group fitness while sacrificing self-fitness. The local Ojash of rural Kamrupa organized a network of Xasang (local temple) based healing systems to activate Avatar Kosha in the entire community during epidemic such as smallpox and cholera.

Figure 5: Schematic of the concept note: The International Vedic Center of Public Health Science, Kendall Square, MIT/Harvard-India initiative

Mission and Visions: Taking forward the “Vishwaguru” mission of Bharat by taking Hindu philosophy to the heart of MIT/Harvard’s Kendall Square’s scientific discourse

Objectives:

1. Application of Vedic Philosophy in basic and clinical bio-medical science (Figure 1-3).
2. Application of Vedic Philosophy in Public Health Science and Global Health Theory (Figure 4)
3. Development of a Vedic philosophy-based Medical Humanities project

Expectations: Our efforts will bring the altruistic philosophy embedded in Veda to the scientific discourse on biological altruism.